

DETAILED EVALUATION OF VISIBLE DEFORMATION IN CFRP LAMINATES SUBJECTED TO OUT-OF-PLANE IMPACT LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Out-of-plane impact loading causes both the internal damage including interlaminar delaminations and the visible deformation on CFRP laminates. The damaged specimens subjected to drop-weight impact were observed in detail by several inspection systems: UT, X-ray CT, and shape measurement systems with laser. The influence of laminate thicknesses, stacking sequences, impactor shapes were observed using cross-ply and quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates. The results showed the bulge with the fiber breakage affects the detectability of the impacted part. By quantitatively evaluating the dent depth and the projected dent area, it showed the possibility that more diverse discussions could be made about dent detectability.

1 INTRODUCTION

Various things such as birds, hail, lightning strikes, tools etc. have the possibility to collide with composite aircraft structures. The current inspection scheme starts with a visual inspection, and if dent or damage is found, it will shift to NDI (Non-Destructive Inspection). The dent found by visual inspection is a mark indicating the possibility of the occurrence of damage. Therefore, visible deformations that occur in composites are of interest in aircraft development / operation. In particular, dent depth is easily detected by human eyes, and it is one of the fundamental judgment criteria in aircraft inspection. Current composite damage tolerance designs assume inspection in the operation of the aircraft and requires setting of dent detectability (dent depth, POD) and energy level, as described in CMH-17-3G [1].

Aviation authorities are considering expanding the types of collisions to be covered in the design in order to respond to unforeseen situations. For example, there is a possibility that the airframe designer will be required in the future to consider the HEWABI (High Energy Wide Area Blur Impact), which has not been required to be comprehensively covered. It is reported that the dent depth is very small in HEWABI and visual inspection is difficult [2, 3]. Furthermore, with the increasing number of new designs that take advantage of the characteristics of CFRP, there is also the possibility that dent depth cannot be used conventionally as a criterion for inspection.

In recent years, inspection devices utilizing moiré interference method [4] and white light scanning method [5], etc. have been proposed as support for visual inspection of aircraft bodies. Combined with automation technology, these become powerful tools, which can contribute to eliminating inspection errors and drastically reducing maintenance costs. By taking advantage of the high measuring accuracy of the latest devices, it has become easy to evaluate the dent on composite skin surfaces three-dimensionally. Despite such a situation, in order to effectively utilize the acquired information, findings concerning visible deformation and internal damage occur in CFRPs is sufficient. In this

study, we investigated visible deformation and internal damages in high performance thermoset CFRP for aircraft primary structures.

2 IMPACT TESTS

2.1 Specimens

CFRP laminates were molded by an autoclave using an epoxy-based unidirectional carbon fiber prepreg (T800S / 3900-2B, Toray) as a material. The stacking sequence is six kinds of cross-ply $[0/90]_{2s}$, $[0/90]_{4s}$, $[0/90]_{6s}$ and quasi-isotropic $[45/0/-45/90]_s$, $[45/0/-45/90]_{2s}$, $[45/0/-45/90]_{3s}$. The plate thickness is 1.5 mm for 8-ply, 3.1 mm for 16-ply, 4.7 mm for 24-ply. After the molding, the specimen was cut into a size of 80 mm square to fit the fixing jig of drop-weight impact test.

2.2 Drop-weight impact

To investigate the influence of the shape of the collision object on the out-of-plane deformation and internal damage of the CFRP laminate, drop weight impact tests were carried out. The four types of jigs shown in Fig.1, 1/2-inch hemisphere (1/2-inch), 1-inch hemisphere (1-inch), conical, flat were alternately attached at the tip of the impactor, and they used for the impact tests. The impact energy was 3.35 J/mm (1/2 of the specified value of ASTM D7136). The test equipment was instrumented, and not only the time history of the load but also the displacement and the energy history of the specimen were acquired.

After the test, unevenness on the surface of the test piece were measured using a non-contact 3D optical profiler (VR-5000/VR-5200, KEYENCE CORPORATION). Internal damage of the specimens was evaluated using an ultrasonic flaw detector (HIS3 LF, KJTD Co., Ltd.) and an X-ray CT scanner (inspeXio SMX-225CTS, SHIMADZU CORPORATION), and a photograph was also taken.

Figure 1: Impactor tip used in the test.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Observation of specimens

The test specimens after impact loading are shown in Fig. 2. In this paper, not all the results are listed, but in the case of the flat-shaped impactor, circular indentations corresponding to the outer edge of the impactor shape are observed in the front surface, and should be generated by contacts with the impactor edge. There were no changes such as cracks and bulges on the back surface. On the other hand, in the conical-shaped impactor, a clearly visible dent was observed on the front surface. The main failure modes of dent formation were fiber breakage and crushing of resin. Also, the amount of fiber breakage on the front surface is large, and there should be impactor penetration into the inside of the specimen. A bending crack (see Fig. 2(b)) was generated on the back surface along the fiber direction, and the crack length tended to become shorter as the thickness of the specimen increased.

In the hemispherical impactor, dents occurred on the front surface regardless of 1/2-inch and 1-inch, and ridge line accompanied by fiber breakage were observed from the dent outer edge. It is presumed that the difference in the interlaminar shear strength has an influence, since the line is generated more in the cross-ply lamination than in the quasi-isotropic lamination. The dent formation was due to plastic deformation of the resin, which was very different from that by the conical-shaped impactor.

There were also cases where slight swelling occurred on the back surface, but the conditions of the occurrence were unclear. From these observations, it is believed that differences in impactor shape lead to differences in dent and near-surface damages.

Figure 2: Specimen appearance after impact loading (30 mm square area near the impact point).

Figure 3: Projection photos by ultrasonic C-scan and the calculated absorbed impact energy.

Figure 4: Cross-sectional images by X-ray CT scanner.

The result of observing the internal damage of the specimen by ultrasonic C-scan is shown in Fig. 3. A cross-sectional image of the central portion of the specimen taken by X-ray CT scanner is shown in Fig. 4. Delamination damage occurred in all the specimens except for the test with flat-shaped impactor. Comparing the results of $[0/90]_{6s}$ and $[45/0/-45/90]_{3s}$ (see Figs. 3(e) and 3(f)), although the applied impact energy and internal damages are similar, the specimen of $[45/0/-45/90]_{3s}$ had smaller dents. This indicates that dent detectability is affected not only by the impactor shape and plate thickness but by the laminate configuration.

3.2 Impact test data

The load-time curve of the specimen of $[0/90]_{4s}$ is shown in Fig. 4(a). The flat-shaped impactor has the shortest contact time with the specimen and the largest peak load. From the fact that the impulse applied to the impactor was large, it is presumed that the energy absorbed by the specimen was small. This can also be confirmed from the load-displacement curve shown in Fig. 4(b). The displacement was obtained from the instrumented impact tester (CEAST 9350, Instron Corporation). The conical-shaped impactor also exhibits a unique load change, and it is believed that the load is greatly reduced before reaching the maximum load, indicating an impactor penetration into the specimen. In addition, it is also believed that the contact time with the specimen is longer than in the case of other shapes of impactors, resulting in internal sequential failure. On the other hand, in the case of the hemispherical impactors, the influence of the impactor size was small and showed similar behaviour. The influence of the impactor shape described here was similarly observed in the specimens of other plate thicknesses and laminated configurations.

The energy absorbed by the specimen was calculated from the load-displacement curve and is shown in Fig. 3. The relationship between the damage size and the energy was not clear except in the case where damage was extremely small as in the flat-shaped impactor. To clarify, it is necessary not only to obtain further impact test data but a detailed assessment of the damage.

Figure 4: Impact test data of $[0/90]_{4S}$ laminated specimen.

3.3 Evaluation of visible deformation

The surface height distribution and cross-sectional profile when an impact load is applied to the $[0/90]_{6S}$ specimen with a 1-inch hemispherical impactor are shown in Fig. 5. Data were acquired by a high precision shape measurement system (KS-1100, KEYENCE CORPORATION) using a laser displacement meter. The dent was due to plastic deformation of the resin, but it has been confirmed that a bulge accompanied by fiber breakage has occurred near the dent. By analyzing and evaluating the measurement data, it is possible to evaluate not only the volume of the dent part, the projected area and the dent depth but the shape of the bulge part. Since the bulge with the fiber breakage affects the detectability of the impacted part, we would like to consider it in the evaluation of impacted part in the future.

Figure 5: Shape measurement of $[0/90]_{6S}$ laminated specimen.

As an example, the results of comparing cross-sectional profiles of 8-ply specimens are summarized in Fig. 6. The dent depth at the impact point was measured from the results of the cross-sectional profile, and the projected dent area was measured by image processing of the surface height distribution. The dent depth of the conical-shaped impactor was extremely large, and the dent depth by the hemispheric-shaped impactor was about 50 to 200 μm . The dent depth by the flat-shaped impactor was extremely small, which was within the practical measurement error of the measurement system. It was found that the dent depth was larger in orthogonal lamination than in quasi-isotropic lamination, and was influenced by the laminate configuration.

When the projected dent area was compared, it was the largest in the case of a 1-inch hemispherical impactor, followed by a 1/2-inch hemispherical, followed by conical and flat. From the viewpoint of dent detectability, the 1-inch hemispherical impactor has a large projected dent area, but the quasi-isotropic specimen has a dent depth smaller than 100 μm , which is not easy to detect. In order to

examine detectability, it means visibility in the case of visual inspection, more data acquisition and dent shape evaluation are required.

Figure 6: Cross-sectional profiles and dent shape evaluation of 8-ply laminated specimen.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a detailed evaluation of visible deformation caused by out-of-plane impact loading on a thermoset CFRP laminate. With some of the data obtained, laminate thicknesses, stacking sequences, and impactor shapes affected not only internal damage but also visible deformation. By quantitatively evaluating the dent depth and the projected dent area, it showed the possibility that more diverse discussions could be made about dent detectability.

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